

AIRBORNE
LABORATORY

Temperature and humidity measurements on the FAAM aircraft. Calibration, processing and uncertainty analysis

Release 1.0

Hannah Price

Jan 13, 2022

CONTENTS

1	Summary & Introduction	1
1.1	Summary	1
1.2	Introduction	1
2	Pressure Measurements	2
2.1	Instrumentation	2
2.2	Data Processing	2
2.3	Uncertainties	3
2.4	Future work	4
3	Temperature measurements	5
3.1	Instrumentation	5
3.2	Indicated temperature: calibration	6
3.3	Indicated temperature: uncertainty	8
3.4	Recovery factor	10
3.5	Combined uncertainty in static air temperature	15
3.6	Performance in cloud	17
3.7	Future work	17
4	Water Vapour Measurements	18
4.1	Instrumentation	18
4.2	Calibration	20
4.3	Data processing	21
4.4	Uncertainty in Buck CR2 data	22
4.5	Calibration of WVSS-II and associated uncertainty	23
4.6	Relative humidity	24
	Bibliography	31

SUMMARY & INTRODUCTION

1.1 Summary

This document describes the calibrations and analyses performed to produce the temperature and humidity parameters in the FAAM core netCDF. We show that almost all of the sources of uncertainty in these measurements are not due to random measurement error, and so will not be reduced by averaging. In this version of the document, descriptions of the temperature measurement is restricted to platinum resistance thermometers. Future versions will include information about thermistors.

1.2 Introduction

Measuring temperature and humidity on an aircraft is not straightforward, and is unavoidably linked with pressure measurements. Air is slowed down and compressed as it enters a housing, meaning that the temperature indicated by a sensor in that housing is higher than the static air temperature outside. To correct for this increase in temperature, the Mach number, calculated from pressure measurements, and a recovery correction are required. The measurement of water vapour is challenging due to the speed of the aircraft, the range of temperature and humidity a hygrometer experiences, and the potential for exposure to saturated conditions. Detailed discussion of these measurement challenges can be found in chapter 2 of *Airborne Measurements for Environmental Research* [Bange *et al.*, n.d.]

This document describes the calibration procedures and data processing involved in producing temperature and humidity data on the FAAM BAe-146 aircraft, as well as listing future planned work. Our goal is to provide an uncertainty parameter alongside each variable in the FAAM core file, calculated for each datapoint, and reported as a standard uncertainty which can be multiplied by a coverage factor $k=2$ by the user, if required, to provide a coverage probability of approximately 95%. For most parameters, the standard uncertainty will represent a combination of the uncertainties arising from all known sources. The method of combining uncertainties will vary according to the application and the extent to which we are able to know how they contribute to the measurement. As will be described in this document, for the meteorological parameters these uncertainties are almost completely due to systematic measurement errors. It is therefore important to note that they will not be reduced if multiple datapoints in the time series are averaged.

In this document we use the definitions of error and uncertainty given in the International Vocabulary of Metrology (VIM) [200:2012, 2012] and NPL Good Practice Guide No. 11 [Bell, 2001]: error is the difference between the measured value and the ‘true value’ of the thing being measured; uncertainty is a quantification of the doubt about the measurement result. Throughout, we refer to two versions of the FAAM post processing framework for data collected on the aircraft, the older v004 [FAAM, n.d.], and the newer v005 [FAAM, n.d.].

PRESSURE MEASUREMENTS

2.1 Instrumentation

The BAe-146 E3001-ARA (G-LUXE) is fitted with a Reduced Vertical Separation Minimum (RVSM) certified altitude keeping system [D. N. Ferguson, 2004, Ferguson, 2000, Ferguson, 2004], providing altitude and airspeed measurements for both pilot and co-pilot independently, and an emergency backup. It is this system that provides the static and dynamic pressure measurements used in post processing for data collected on the aircraft. Data is sent to the rear core console via the ARINC 429 data bus at approximately 20 Hz, and is interpolated to 32 Hz.

2.2 Data Processing

(See `p_rio_rvsm.py`, `p_rvsm.py`, `p_dry_mach.py` and `p_wet_mach.py`)

Although the RVSM system is fundamentally a set of static and dynamic pressure measurements, the data is sent as a pressure altitude and indicated airspeed. The pressure altitude is converted (back) to static pressure, parameter `PS_RVSM`, using the ICAO standard atmosphere. That static pressure and the indicated airspeed are converted to Mach number, using the equation:

$$M = \frac{V_{IAS}}{V_0 \sqrt{\frac{P}{P_0}}} \quad (2.1)$$

where $V_0 = 340.294$ m/s, $P_0 = 1013.25$ mb, P is the static pressure and V_{IAS} is the indicated air speed. Mach and static pressure are then used to find the dynamic pressure, parameter `Q_RVSM`:

$$Q = P \left(\frac{M^2}{5} + 1 \right)^{\frac{7}{2}} - 1$$

In post processing v004 [FAAM, n.d.], the Mach number used was that calculated using equation (2.1). In post processing v005 [FAAM, n.d.], the humidity-dependent equation for Mach was introduced as follows:

$$M_{moist} = \sqrt{\frac{2c_v}{R_a} \left(\left(1 + \frac{Q}{P} \right)^{\frac{R_a}{c_p}} - 1 \right)} \quad (2.2)$$

where c_p is the specific heat capacity at constant pressure of moist air, c_v is the specific heat capacity at constant volume of moist air, R_a is the specific gas constant of moist air, P is the static pressure from the RVSM system and Q is the dynamic pressure from the RVSM system. c_p , c_v and R_a are calculated as described in Appendix 1 of Khelif et al. 1998 [D. Khelif, 1998]. Specific humidity, q_h , is calculated using the calibrated volume mixing ratio measurement from the flush-mounted WVSS-II (see section *Water Vapour Measurements*), as follows:

$$q_h = \frac{w \cdot 10^{-6} \frac{M_w}{M_d}}{w \cdot 10^{-6} \frac{M_w}{M_d} + 1}$$

where M_w is the molar mass of water, 18.01528 g/mol, M_d is the molar mass of dry air, 28.9644 g/mol, and w is the calibrated WVSS-II water vapour mixing ratio in ppm (parameter `WVSS2_VMR_C`). The specific heat capacity

at constant pressure, c_p , and constant volume, c_v , are given by:

$$c_p = \frac{7}{2} R_d \left(1 + q_h \left(\frac{8}{7 \frac{M_w}{M_d}} - 1 \right) \right) \quad (2.3)$$

$$c_v = \frac{5}{2} R_d \left(1 + q_h \left(\frac{6}{5 \frac{M_w}{M_d}} - 1 \right) \right) \quad (2.4)$$

where R_d is the specific gas constant for dry air, $287.058 \text{ J kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, and the moist air gas constant, $R_a = c_p - c_v$. In the rare case that humidity data is not available, post processing v005 reverts to calculating the Mach number using equation (2.1).

2.3 Uncertainties

Neither of the RVSM pressure measurements could be described as calibrated in a scientific sense since their main purpose is for aviation. They are maintained by aircraft engineers, and checked regularly for compliance with aviation regulations [Authority, n.d., Ferguson, 2000], but they do not have calibrations applied which are traceable to national scientific standards.

The measurement of static pressure at a static port on an aircraft is always subject to systematic error related to the position of the static port on the aircraft body [Ferguson, 2000]. This position error can be quantified by experiment, and BAE have determined a velocity-dependent position error correction, named the -903 Law, for AVRO 146-RJ aircraft. The BAe-146 E3001-ARA (G-LUXE) is sufficiently aerodynamically similar to the 146-RJ aircraft that the -903 law can be used for its RVSM certification. Residual errors exist, and were measured for some flight conditions in the early 2000s by comparison with a trailing cone (a free stream measurement of static pressure achieved by trailing a cone behind the aircraft [D. N. Ferguson, 2004]). Those measured residual errors were found to be a function of velocity, altitude and, to lesser extent at science speed, aircraft weight. Since those trailing cone flights, G-LUXE's nose cone has been replaced, and additional science instrumentation fitted. No residual error correction is applied in the FAAM post processing, so there remains a systematic error. That error is small enough to disregard for RVSM certification, but nevertheless results a small bias in the pressure measurements.

An intercomparison flight with the DLR HALO aircraft (which has a very well characterised static pressure measurement, [A. Giez and Mallaun, 2019]) in July 2017 shows that FAAM's RVSM static pressure error could be 1-2 mb below 10 kft, with no data available above 10 kft. Applying a correction for the residual position error according to the data collected during trailing cone flights in the early 2000s does not improve agreement with HALO.

Despite their deficiencies, the static and dynamic pressures derived from the RVSM system are the best pressure measurements currently available on the FAAM aircraft, so an estimate of their uncertainties is required in order to determine the uncertainties in other measurements made downstream. Using the intercomparison flights with HALO as our current best source of comparison data, we estimate an uncertainty in the RVSM static pressure measurement, PS_RVSM, of 2 mb. The BAe146 Series 300 Certificate of Airworthiness Report No. 126 [Poole, 1988] shows that there is a residual Mach number correction of up to 0.005 for a science speed of 210 kts, and in the absence of a more thorough uncertainty analysis we take this as an estimate of uncertainty in Mach from the RVSM system.

The uncertainty contribution from the water vapour measurement used in the calculation of moist Mach in equation (2.2) was calculated by propagation of uncertainties through equation (2.2), and can be approximated by

$$u(M_{humidity}) = 2.1155 \cdot 10^{-17} w^3 - 8.8891 \cdot 10^{-13} w^2 + 1.5918 \cdot 10^{-8} w + 3.2179 \cdot 10^{-5}$$

where w is the calibrated volume mixing ratio from the WVSS-II in ppm. Combining with 'uncertainty' associated with the residual Mach number correction, M_{res} of 0.005:

$$u(M) = \sqrt{u(M_{res})^2 + u(M_{humidity})^2} \quad (2.5)$$

The uncertainty in moist Mach due to the uncertainty in the water vapour measurement, $u(M_{humidity})$, is orders of magnitude smaller than the 'uncertainty' associated with the residual Mach number correction, but has been included for completeness.

2.4 Future work

Since the HALO intercomparison flight in summer 2017, a new science static pressure measurement has been fitted to the FAAM aircraft at port S10, but its static position error has not yet been characterised. To quantify the static position error requires further trailing cone flights, comparison with a pacer aircraft with a well-characterised static pressure measurement, tower fly-bys, height monitoring unit overflights, or some combination of these. It is hoped that characterisation work will soon be undertaken so that a position error correction can be applied to the static pressure measurement at S10 and the dynamic pressure measurement at P0 and S10. This will then provide traceable static and dynamic pressure measurements, and subsequently Mach, for use in post processing.

TEMPERATURE MEASUREMENTS

3.1 Instrumentation

Fig. 3.1: The de-iced (foreground) and non-de-iced (background) Rosemount Type 102 housings fitted to the FAAM aircraft.

On board the FAAM aircraft, air temperature is measured via internal sensors in two Rosemount Model 102 housings [T. M. Stickney, 1994], one de-iced (configuration B), the other non-de-iced, as shown in Fig. 3.1. Both housings employ similar inlets to draw flow across the sensing elements, designed to minimise water and particle ingress, as well as minimising interaction of the air with the inlet walls. The housings are designed to, as far as possible, bring the air to rest relative to the aircraft. As the air enters the housings, it slows and is compressed, increasing its temperature. The sensors inside the housings are resistance based thermometers - either platinum resistance thermometers or thermistors. Their resistance is measured using a circuit at the rear core console designed and built in-house. They measure a temperature known as the indicated temperature, T_i , which is higher than the static air temperature outside the aircraft. T_i is close to the total air temperature (the maximum air temperature which would be attained by complete conversion of the kinetic energy of the air in the housing), T_{tot} . Our measured temperature, T_i , must be converted to the more useful static air temperature, T_s , also known as the true air temperature (parameters TAT_DI_R and TAT_ND_R).

The static air temperature, T_s , is related to the total air temperature by

$$\frac{T_{tot}}{T_s} = 1 + \left(\frac{\gamma - 1}{2} \right) \times M^2 \quad (3.1)$$

where γ is the ratio of the specific heat capacities. This was taken to be 1.4 in post processing v004, and replaced with $\frac{c_p}{c_v}$ in post processing v005, calculated using the equations for moist air specific heats given in Khelif et al. (1998), shown here in equations (2.3) and (2.4). M is the Mach number (dry air Mach in v004 and moist Mach in v005) from the RVSM system, described in section *Pressure Measurements*.

The total temperature is related to the indicated temperature by a recovery factor, as discussed in section *Recovery factor*.

3.2 Indicated temperature: calibration

The original type 102 sensing elements were constructed using a loom of thin platinum wire, as shown in Fig. 3.2 (left), the resistance of which changes with temperature. These sensors have been used on the aircraft for many years, although several issues with their continued usage have arisen:

- The low thermal mass of the thin platinum wire means that the response of part of these probes to changing air temperature is fast. However the mica support responds more slowly to temperature fluctuations, and as such the probes exhibit two time constants [C. A. Friehe, 1992].
- The fragile platinum wire loom can easily be damaged in-flight, causing long-term probe degradation ranging from calibration drifts over time to complete probe failure, as demonstrated in Fig. 3.3.
- There is a dwindling stock of these loom-type sensors at FAAM. The manufacturer, now UTC Aerospace, no longer routinely produces these sensors.

An alternative solution was developed at FAAM which utilises the existing Rosemount housings but replaces the platinum loom with two thin-film IST MiniSens PT100 platinum resistance thermometers (referred to here as “plate-type”), wired in parallel, shown in Fig. 3.2 (right). These modified sensors have been shown to be robust and maintain a stable calibration over the course of many months’ flying. The use of two sensing elements, as opposed to one, means that flight data can be recovered if one element fails - a re-calibration of the remaining element is all that is required. When two of these sensors are fitted to the aircraft (one in each housing), they consistently give agreement between the de-iced and non-de-iced temperature measurements better than 0.1 °C. The drawback to these sensors is their response time. Despite their small size, they still have a greater thermal mass than the thin platinum loom of the original Rosemount sensors and are thus comparatively slow to respond to temperature fluctuations. With time response being equivalent to spatial resolution for an airborne platform, a third option for temperature measurement using thermistors is under development and described in FAAM013005.

There are two stages of calibration involved in producing the indicated temperature measurement: quantifying the relationship between each sensor’s resistance and temperature, and quantifying of the relationship between resistance and ‘counts’ measured on the aircraft data system (known as DECADES).

The resistance, R , to temperature, T_i calibration is done at the National Physical Laboratory (NPL), after a sensor has been fitted for 30 flights or when drift is suspected. At NPL, sensors are calibrated in a test chamber, in air, and compared with reference PRTs at 10 K intervals between 213 K and 323 K. Each calibration certificate states:

Fig. 3.2: An original “loom”-type PRT sensor (left) and a modified “plate”-type sensor (right).

Fig. 3.3: The final few minutes of flight B944, during which the loom-type PRT sensor in the de-iced housing failed at 14:36. The plate-type sensor in the non-de-iced housing was unaffected.

“Traceability of measurement was provided by calibration of the reference thermometers to the International Temperature Scale of 1990 (ITS-90) through NPL Temperature Standard. As requested the PRTs were monitored using a precision resistance bridge with traceability to national standards, using an excitation current of 2.8 mA. At each generated condition a time of not less than 60 minutes was allowed for temperature to equilibrate. A set of 10 readings recorded at 1 minute intervals was then taken from the instruments under test.”

The resulting calibration points are fit using a quadratic curve to produce a parameterisation for R vs T_i .

At FAAM, we perform calibrations (‘DECADES calibrations’) of the resistance/voltage to ‘counts’ relationship of the relevant channels on the aircraft data system at least once per year. These DECADES calibrations involve replacing temperature sensors with fixed resistors, at $3\ \Omega$ intervals between $35\ \Omega$ and $65\ \Omega$, and recording the counts at each calibration point for 10 seconds. The resistance of the fixed resistors are measured using a Keithley 197 digital multimeter (DVM), which is regularly calibrated. The resulting calibration points are used to produce a linear fit for counts vs R , which is combined with the quadratic R vs T_i to convert from counts to indicated temperature.

3.3 Indicated temperature: uncertainty

For the PRT sensors, the combined uncertainty in indicated temperature is calculated by summation in quadrature using a spreadsheet model, as described, for example, in 9.2 of NPL Good Practice Guide No. 11 [Bell, 2001]¹. Table 3.1 lists the known sources of uncertainty in indicated temperature, along with the likely probability distribution associated with each source. Where these are uncertainties in resistance or counts, they have been converted to equivalent uncertainties in temperature by applying a typical calibration for a $50\ \Omega$ PRT.

¹ For the thermistors, due to the complexity of the self-heating analysis (described in FAAM013005), a Monte Carlo-type analysis will be performed.

Table 3.1: Sources of uncertainty associated with temperature measurements.

Source	Loom	Plate	Distribution	Divisor	Description
Sensor Drift	0.24	0.025	Assumed normal	1	Repeatability of R to T_i calibrations. Calculated from the drift between calibrations of the same sensor over years. Greater for looms than for plates.
NPL calibration residual	0.0057	0.013	Assumed normal	1	Uncertainty associated with quadratic fit applied to NPL R to T_i calibration. Taken to be the residual standard deviation over all calibration points

Source	DI	NDI	Distribution	Divisor	Description
DECADES cal. variation	0.21	0.12	Assumed normal	1	Repeatability of DECADES calibrations, estimated using the standard deviation across many years of calibrations performed using the same set of resistors
DECADES cal. residual	0.094	0.024	Assumed normal	1	Uncertainty associated with the linear fit applied to the DECADES calibration. Taken to be the residual standard deviation over all calibration points
Noise with fixed resistor	0.0030	0.0028	Assumed normal	1	Noise recorded when fixed resistor fitted to the aircraft in place of sensing element.

Source	All	Distribution	Divisor	Description
Keithley DVM calibration	0.04	Assumed normal	1	Uncertainty associated with calibration of digital multimeter, provided on its calibration certificate.
Keithley DVM stability	0.02	Assumed normal	1	Temperature stability of digital multimeter, provided on specifications sheet.
Keithley DVM resolution uncertainty	0.0025	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	Resolution of digital multimeter
NPL resistance measurement	0.0025	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	Half the final quoted digit in resistance measurements supplied on NPL calibration certificates
DECADES resolution uncertainty	0.0004	Rectangular	$\sqrt{3}$	Resolution of the aircraft data acquisition system, i.e. K per DECADES count.

Source	T dependent	Distribution	Divisor	Description
NPL calibration uncertainty	0.04	Assumed normal	1	Provided on the NPL calibration certificate, varies with indicated temperature

3.4 Recovery factor

Due to the inability to reach complete adiabatic compression within the Rosemount housings, the temperature indicated by the sensors, T_i , is less than T_{tot} . To account for this, a recovery factor is required. Rosemount state in Technical Report 5755 [T. M. Stickney, 1994] that their Type 102 sensors exhibit a variable recovery factor below a Mach number of 1. They define this variable recovery factor as

$$\eta = \frac{T_{tot} - T_i}{T_{tot}} \quad (3.2)$$

and provide plots of η vs Mach number based on wind tunnel measurements. The values of η provided in the report for the de-iced housing (Model 102 configuration B) are applicable to fully encased platinum resistance thermometers, hermetically sealed in the wall of a platinum shell with a radiation shield, which are not used at FAAM. For the non-de-iced housing, η values are provided for an open wire element - the platinum loom-type sensors originally used at FAAM. The report states that when an open wire sensor is used in either configuration of the de-iced housing, performance will be “comparable”, yet no data is provided. This lack of information about how η varies with Mach in the de-iced housing has led to the recovery factors for both housings being determined using flight data.

3.4.1 Constant recovery factor, r (v004)

(See `p_rio_temps.py` [FAAM, n.d.])

Attempts have been made in the past to measure a constant recovery factor, r , on the FAAM aircraft, defined as

$$r = \frac{T_i - T_s}{T_{tot} - T_s}$$

Assuming a constant adiabatic recovery factor,

$$\frac{T_i}{T_s} = 1 + \left(r \times \frac{\gamma - 1}{2} \times M^2 \right) \quad (3.3)$$

By flying at different speeds through air of constant temperature, plots of T_i vs M^2 can be obtained. (3.3) can be rearranged to

$$T_i = T_s + rT_s \left(\frac{\gamma - 1}{2} \right) M^2 \quad (3.4)$$

The gradient and y-intercept of a linear fit to T_i vs M^2 allows r to be determined for each housing. Unfortunately, the resulting values of r are variable, possibly due to small changes in static air temperature during measurements or errors in the measurement of the static and dynamic pressure. Nevertheless, values of r calculated from this analysis (0.9928 for the de-iced housing and 0.999 for the non-de-iced housing) were used in v004 of the post processing. The agreement between the de-iced and the non-de-iced static air temperatures calculated using these constant recovery factors is better than when calculated using the variable recovery factors given in the Rosemount report. However, agreement between the two housings does not necessarily mean that either measurement is accurate.

3.4.2 Variable recovery factor, η (v005)

(See `p_recovery_factor.py` [FAAM, n.d.] and `p_prt_temps.py` [FAAM, n.d.])

Discussions with Collins Aerospace in December 2020 confirmed that the Rosemount 5755 report [T. M. Stickney, 1994] contains reliable data for the recovery factor of open-wire sensors in the non-de-iced housing, but does not contain that data for the de-iced housing. This information, combined with the fact that a new, low-noise circuit for measuring the resistances of the temperature sensors was installed in December 2017, means that we can now estimate the variable recovery factor for the de-iced housing based on the assumption that the non-de-iced recovery factor provided in the Rosemount 5755 report is correct. The following describes the analysis implemented in `deiced_recovery_factor_prt_only_2021.py` [Price, n.d.] .

Following on from equations (3.1) and (3.2),

$$\frac{T_i}{T_s} = (1 - \eta) \left(1 + \frac{\gamma - 1}{2} \times M^2 \right) \quad (3.5)$$

The static temperature, T_s measured by both housings should be the same:

$$\frac{T_{i,n}}{(1 - \eta_n) \left(1 + \frac{\gamma - 1}{2} \times M^2 \right)} = \frac{T_{i,d}}{(1 - \eta_d) \left(1 + \frac{\gamma - 1}{2} \times M^2 \right)}$$

The M^2 terms cancel, and rearranging:

$$\eta_d = 1 - \frac{T_{i,n}}{T_{i,d}} (1 - \eta_n)$$

For the Mach range of the FAAM aircraft (0.2 to 0.7), the data shown in Figure 20 in the Rosemount 5755 report can be described by:

$$\begin{aligned} \eta_n &= -6.0943146 \times 10^{-4} M^2 + 1.4054157 \times 10^{-3} M \\ \sigma_{\eta_n} &= -3.4581190 \times 10^{-4} M^2 + 5.9345748 \times 10^{-4} M \end{aligned} \quad (3.6)$$

(σ_{η_n} is calculated from the error band shown in Figure 20 of the Rosemount 5755 report, confirmed by Collins Aerospace to represent the 2:math:sigma uncertainty).

Using flight data for the ratio of the indicated temperatures, $\frac{T_{i,n}}{T_{i,d}}$, we can calculate thousands of “measurements” of η_d across a range of Mach. The analysis was restricted to cloud-free, straight and level runs. To achieve this, the data was filtered so that measurements collected under the following conditions were removed:

- profiles up or down (filtered by assessing angle of attack and successive changes in static pressure)
- possibility of cloud (difference between the static temperature and the dewpoint measured by the General Eastern chilled mirror hygrometer less than 2 K)
- on the ground
- magnitude of the roll greater than 0.5 degree
- angle of attack greater than 8 degrees or less than 3 degrees
- large difference (greater than 1 K) between the two static air temperatures calculated using the standard constant recovery factors (this is to filter out instances of sensor damage or poor calibration)

Initial analysis was performed for flights between December 2017 and March 2020 where a PRT sensor (either “loom”, the original wound wire sensors from Rosemount, or “plate”, a modified version using a commercially sourced thin film PRT) was fitted in both housings. A small minority of flights are excluded due to issues with sensors, leaving a total of 49 flights. Fig. 3.4 shows each measurement of the ratio of the indicated temperatures, as a function of Mach number. No strong dependency of the ratio on Mach number is observed, so η_d is calculated using the average ratio, α , such that

$$\eta_d = 1 - \alpha (1 - \eta_n)$$

The uncertainty in the variable recovery factor calculated for the de-iced housing is therefore:

$$\sigma_{\eta_d}^2 = (\eta_n - 1)^2 \sigma_{\alpha}^2 + \alpha^2 \sigma_{\eta_n}^2 \quad (3.7)$$

The resulting values of the mean ratio, α , and its standard deviation, σ_{α} are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha &= 0.9989 \\ \sigma_{\alpha} &= 0.0006 \end{aligned}$$

Fig. 3.5 shows each calculated value of η_d as a grey datapoint, along with a dashed red line showing η_d calculated using the average ratio of indicated temperatures (i.e. using equations 10 and 12, with the value of α given in 14). Fig. 3.6 shows a histogram of the differences between the true air temperatures calculated for each housing (de-iced true air temperature – non-de-iced true air temperature). It can be seen that changing from the old constant

Fig. 3.4: The ratio, $\frac{T_{i,n}}{T_{i,d}}$, of indicated temperatures, vs Mach, for flights for which a PRT was fitted in each housing. A plate-type sensor was always fitted in the de-iced housing. Light grey points come from flights when a plate-type sensor was also fitted in the non-de-iced housing; dark grey points comes from flights where a loom-type sensor was fitted in the non-de-iced housing. Data shown is collected using a variety of individual sensors - two different looms, and six different PRTs, resulting in a total of six configurations.

Fig. 3.5: Calculated values of η_d for flights when a plate-type sensor was fitted in the de-iced housing and a loom-type sensor was fitted in the non-de-iced housing (dark grey points) and flights when a plate-type sensor was fitted in both housings (light grey points). Overlaid as a dashed red line is the curve of η_d calculated using the average ratio of indicated temperatures, α . The black dashed line is a reproduction of the line given in Figure 20 of Rosemount report 5755 for the variable recovery factor of the non-de-iced housing. Uncertainty bands represent the 1σ uncertainty for each η .

Fig. 3.6: Histograms to show the difference between the true (static) air temperature (TAT or T_s) measurements in each housing, for flights where a PRT was fitted in each housing. Data calculated using the fixed recovery factors is shown in grey; the same calculated using the new variable recovery factors is shown in green.

recovery factors, r_d and r_n , to the new variable recovery factors, η_d and η_n , we reduce the mean difference between our two true air temperature measurements by 0.225 K. The change from using r to η increases the non-de-iced true air temperature by around 0.1 K, and increases the de-iced true air temperature by around 0.3 K.

In summary, the variable recovery factor for the non-de-iced housing provided in Rosemount 5755 is implemented in v005 of the post processing, along with the variable recovery factor calculated here for the de-iced housing, based on flights where a PRT is fitted in both housings:

$$\begin{aligned}\eta_n &= -6.0943146 \times 10^{-4} M^2 + 1.4054157 \times 10^{-3} M \\ \sigma_{\eta_n} &= -3.4581190 \times 10^{-4} M^2 + 5.9345748 \times 10^{-4} M \\ \eta_d &= 1 - \alpha (1 - \eta_n) \\ \sigma_{\eta_d}^2 &= (\eta_n - 1)^2 \sigma_\alpha^2 + \alpha^2 \sigma_{\eta_n}^2\end{aligned}$$

with $\alpha = 0.9989$ and $\sigma_\alpha = 0.0006$.

The uncertainty in η_n due to any uncertainty in Mach is negligible in comparison with the uncertainty given in Rosemount Report 5755 [T. M. Stickney, 1994]. Since η_d is empirically determined using Mach on our aircraft, and the most significant source of uncertainty in Mach is the position error (and will therefore not vary between the measurements made in the determination of η_d and measurements made in general), the uncertainty in η_d due to uncertainty in Mach is also considered to be negligible, and comes from the uncertainty in η_n and the uncertainty relating to the empirical determination.

Further work on recovery factors will include:

- A further assessment of any Mach dependence in the ratio of indicated temperatures, and thus the validity of using α . There may be a hint of a decrease in the ratio at high Mach number.
- Expanding the analysis to thermistor sensors.
- Collecting more data for at high altitude, especially with a loom-type PRT fitted in the de-iced housing.

3.5 Combined uncertainty in static air temperature

(See `p_prt_uncertainties.py` [FAAM, n.d.]

Finding the uncertainty in static air temperature, $u(T_s)$ (reported in the core file as parameters TAT_ND_R_CU and TAT_DI_R_CU), requires combining the uncertainties in indicated temperature, T_i , of the sensor, the Mach number, M , the ratio of specific heats, γ , and the recovery factor, η (no uncertainty in recovery factor r is available). The combined uncertainty in T_s is calculated according to the law of propagation of uncertainty as defined in section 5 of the ISO/IEC Guide to the Expression of Uncertainty in Measurement [ISO/IEC, 2008]:

$$u^2(T_s) = \left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial T_i}\right)^2 u^2(T_i) + \left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \eta}\right)^2 u^2(\eta) + \left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial M}\right)^2 u^2(M) + \left(\frac{\partial T_s}{\partial \gamma}\right)^2 u^2(\gamma) \quad (3.8)$$

$u(T_i)$ is calculated using the summation in quadrature of the sources of uncertainty listed in Table 3.1, for the relevant configuration. $u(M)$ is given by equation (2.5). $u(\eta)$ is given by either equation (3.6) or (3.7). Although η is Mach-dependent, given the inherent uncertainty in both η_n and η_d are significantly larger than any uncertainty that would be introduced because of an error in Mach, and given the empirical nature of the method used to determine η_d for our aircraft, we neglect an contribution to the uncertainty in η from the uncertainty in Mach. The uncertainty in γ resulting from the uncertainty in the volume mixing ratio measurement from the WVSS-II (see section *Water Vapour Measurements*) was calculated by propagation of uncertainties through equations (2.3) and (2.4). The resulting uncertainty can be approximated as follows:

$$u(\gamma) = 9.4264 \cdot 10^{-17} w^3 - 3.7152 \cdot 10^{-12} w^2 + 5.6828 \cdot 10^{-8} w + 6.3904 \cdot 10^{-5}$$

where w is the water vapour volume mixing ratio in ppm.

Fig. 3.7 shows the relative contributions of each term in equation (3.8): it can be seen that the terms associated with uncertainty in T_i and M are the largest, with the uncertainty in η smaller but still significant. The contribution from the uncertainty associated with γ is negligible.

Fig. 3.7: Relative contributions of each term in equation (3.8) over the course of a flight.

3.6 Performance in cloud

Both types of Rosemount Model 102 housings can be affected by liquid water and icing, introducing errors in the reported true air temperature which are not included in the uncertainty calculations described above. Liquid water on a sensing element can change its temperature, as can the effect of evaporative cooling. In icing conditions, the housings can clog with ice, meaning that there is little airflow and thus the sensors do not measure the true air temperature. The non-de-iced housing is less susceptible to liquid water ingress than the de-iced housing, whilst the de-iced housing is less susceptible to being clogged with ice. The effect of water or ice is only evident by comparing data from sensors in the two housings: where they agree, the data is likely to be good, but where they disagree it is often impossible to say which, if either, is reading the correct temperature.

3.7 Future work

The uncertainty in static air temperature can be reduced most significantly by reducing the uncertainty and correcting the systematic position error which affects the static and dynamic pressures. The next biggest improvement will be in improving the DECADES calibration by using a highly accurate, self-adjusting programmable resistance box (recently purchased). Uncertainty quantification for the thermistor sensors using a Monte Carlo-type method is required, once a new PCB has been finalised.

WATER VAPOUR MEASUREMENTS

4.1 Instrumentation

There are currently three types of hygrometers in use on the FAAM aircraft. Two of these are chilled mirror hygrometers (the General Eastern 1011B, and the Buck CR2), the third is the Water Vapor Sensing System (WVSS-II) from SpectraSensors. The Buck CR2 and WVSS-II are used in combination to produce a calibrated volume mixing ratio measurement with a response time of around 2 s. The General Eastern hygrometer is operated as a backup instrument.

4.1.1 General Eastern

The 1011B thermoelectric hygrometer measures the dewpoint of ambient air using the chilled mirror technique. Air is sampled using a passive inlet, nominally free of any particles, and passed over a mirror. The mirror is thermoelectrically cooled until it reaches a temperature at which condensation begins to form (the dew or frost point), and is then held at that temperature. The presence of condensation is sensed optically. By definition this is an absolute measurement of dewpoint temperature.

An inlet is mounted on the aircraft skin permitting sampling of the ambient airstream. A pressure gradient is created in flight using the difference in flow across two ports, and the ambient air is thus passed through the internal portion of the inlet containing the mirror and sample optics. A control module is mounted on the Aft Core Console providing a visual display of the humidity as well as a user interface. Power for these components is supplied by a further electronics unit on the aft core console, which also outputs the measurements to the aircraft data system.

GE “dewpoint” data are recorded at 4 Hz by the aircraft data recording system. “Dewpoint” measurements output by the GE, parameter TDEW_GE are in fact readings of the mirror temperature. Under many circumstances this is almost equivalent to dew/frost point with the following caveats:

- The GE is nominally capable of measuring data in the dew point range -75 to $+50$ °C. Its actual capability is strongly dependent on the ambient temperature and the instrument data are typically subject to increasing positive bias below around -25 °C, possibly due to temperature effects in flight. The instrument time response depends on the phase of the condensate layer and the mirror temperature. At dewpoints around 0 °C the response time might be expected to be of the order of a few seconds, becoming many minutes at -40 °C and below. Data acquired in these conditions should therefore be used with caution.
- As is typical of chilled mirror instruments, the GE data mirror data become ambiguous between 0 °C and -30 °C in which range it is often difficult to distinguish the phase of the condensate layer. This is important since ice and water have different saturation vapour pressures at a given temperature. To put it another way, for a given ambient humidity level, the dew and frost points will be different by a known, non-trivial amount. Since it is not obvious whether the mirror temperature reported is a frost or a dew point, the true ambient humidity cannot be determined from the mirror temperature alone. Supercooled liquid water typically only has lifetimes of tens of minutes on the GE mirror, and below -40 °C homogenous freezing will occur. FAAM have not seen instances of a GE liquid water layer below -30 °C. Careful examination of the data by the user may therefore be required with this instrument to distinguish the mirror phase and therefore the true ambient humidity.

- No correction is made for pressure. There is no pressure measurement within the GE inlet or sample chamber. For there to be flow through the inlet there must be a small reduction in the pressure in the inlet below ambient static pressure. Although small, this is unknown.
- GE dewpoint measurements can be positively biased in cloud, as the sampling method appears to allow cloud water into the sample chamber which then floods the mirror.

This instrument is no longer routinely calibrated. Dewpoint data from the Buck CR2 chilled mirror hygrometer should be used instead where possible. Where Buck CR2 data is unavailable, data from the General Eastern may be used, but only after careful comparison between the Buck and General Eastern for preceding flights.

4.1.2 Buck CR2

The Buck CR2 hygrometer measures atmospheric dewpoint using the chilled mirror technique. There are currently two Buck CR2 units at FAAM, serial numbers 211-M and 219-M, but it is only possible to fit one at a time to the aircraft. The CR2-211-M was first fitted to the aircraft in August 2008 and was used intermittently until January 2016, when the CR2-219-M was fitted in its place. Several problems have been detected with both instruments and both have been returned to the manufacturer for repair and modification several times.

Air is extractively pumped through an inlet into a sample chamber and passed over a mirror-like metal surface. The mirror temperature is regulated using a Stirling cycle cooler until condensation begins to form on the mirror, this being the dew or frost point in the chamber. The condensation layer is maintained at a constant level using optical detection and control, and the mirror temperature is measured using an embedded platinum resistance thermometer or thermistor.

The CR2 sample inlet consists of a pumped reverse-facing inlet and outlet mounted around 1.8 m back from the nose of the aircraft. The inlet pipes are made of stainless steel and are linked to the CR2 instrument by a stainless steel line with an internal hydrophobic coating. The sample line is heated to 50 °C to increase the mobility of adsorbed water. The CR2 is mounted around 60 cm from the inlet, within the aircraft skin compartment. Data are transmitted using an RS232 link. Power for the CR2, pump and heater, and conversion from RS232 to ethernet are catered for in an auxiliary electronics unit. The sample mass flow is controlled to 1 litre per minute by means of a downstream flow controller and pump. The CR2 outputs measurements of its mirror temperature data at 1 Hz, along with other state parameters used to define the stability of the mirror condensation layer. The uncorrected mirror temperature is included in the core file as parameter TDEW_CR2

Both CR2 instruments have been seen to exhibit “cold-soaking”. This occurs when the aircraft descends rapidly from high altitude into warmer, moist air. The metal optics block has a high thermal mass and thus warms up slowly in comparison to the air flowing through the chamber. It is thought that condensation occurring on the window between the mirror chamber and the optics “blinds” the instrument. It can no longer “see” what is happening on the mirror, so assumes the mirror needs to be cleaned, and performs a heating and cooling cycle accordingly. This results in unusable data and is a common problem in detachment flying at hot locations. To address the issue, a heater surrounded by insulation has been wrapped around the outside of the optics block of the CR2-219-M, which solved the problem. The same heater has been implemented on the CR2-211-M but it was removed by the manufacturer during a repair and has yet to be reinstated.

4.1.3 WVSS-II

The WVSS-II was designed for commercial air carriers by UCAR/SpectraSensors, and it is possible to fit up to two units on the FAAM aircraft at windows 6 and 7. Two types of inlet are available, the most commonly used being a purpose-built certified UCAR inlet on the aircraft skin which removes liquid water from the sample stream, to improve measurements in cloud. Although low-profile it is potentially susceptible to icing and has no heater, and this low-profile itself may be problematic, promoting measurement from within the aircraft boundary layer. The other type of inlet is a modified Rosemount Type 102 inlet, mounted on a short pylon to locate its mouth 12 cm from the skin, believed to place it outside the aircraft’s boundary layer. It has been shown that the modified Rosemount Type 102 inlet is susceptible to ingesting cloud particles.

A measurement is made just inside the aircraft with a tuneable diode laser (TDL) absorption technique using a single wavelength at 1.37 μ m and a 24 cm path length with 2nd harmonic detection. Volume mixing ratio data

is reported approximately once every 2.3 s, and is interpolated to 1 Hz in the core processing to produce parameters WVSS2F_VMR_U and WVSS2R_VMR_U, for the flush and Rosemount inlets, respectively (or WVSS2F_VMR and WVSS2R_VMR prior to the introduction of the WVSS-II calibration described in section ref{wvss2cal}). FAAM have three WVSS-II units, serial numbers 4229, 0388 and 4252. 4252 is currently fitted using the flush inlet at window 6 and is the only unit for which an in-flight calibration analysis has been completed (see section ref{wvss2cal}).

4.1.4 Humidity calibration equipment in FAAM labs

Prior to 2019, the two Buck CR2 units were routinely sent to NPL for calibration. More recently, a calibration facility has been set up in the FAAM labs so that aircraft hygrometers can be calibrated in-house. The lab equipment consists of a Michell Instruments PSD2 pressure swing drier, a Michell Instruments DG2 dew point generator, and an MBW 973-L transfer standard chilled mirror hygrometer. Tubing from the PSD2 to the DG2 and on to the MBW 973-L and test hygrometers is stainless steel of internal diameter $\frac{1}{4}$ inch or 6 mm.

4.2 Calibration

4.2.1 Calibration of lab equipment

The MBW 973-L hygrometer is calibrated yearly at NPL to achieve traceability to ITS-90, with calibration points at no more than 20 °C intervals between -70 and +20 °C. The NPL calibration certificate states:

“The calibration was carried out against NPL Standard Humidity Generators, in terms of dew-point temperature. The ‘generated dew point’ was determined from measurements made using platinum resistance thermometers (PRTs). Traceability of the measurement was provided by calibration of these thermometers to the International Temperature Scale of 1990 (ITS-90) through NPL Temperature Standards.

Before use, the hygrometer mirror was cleaned successively with deionised water, isopropyl alcohol and then again with deionised water using cotton buds. Following each cleaning the mirror enclosure was dried in a stream of clean dry air.

Air of a known dew-point temperature, at a pressure of 105.0 kPa, was supplied to the test hygrometer inlet. At dew-point temperatures below 0 °C a 1.3 m length of 3 mm internal diameter stainless steel tubing was used. At dew-point temperature above 0 °C a 1.2 m length of 4 mm internal diameter PTFE tubing was used. The moist air was then vented to atmosphere, through a rotameter with a needle valve assembly for flow control. The air flow rate was set so that the flow through the test hygrometer was nominally 0.5 litres per minute, as measured by an additional rotameter on the exhaust of the hygrometer.

The measurement procedure was as follows: (a) the temperature of the thermostatically controlled NPL Generator bath containing a primed saturator was set (b) air was circulated through the pipework and the NPL Generator system was allowed to come to equilibrium (c) the hygrometer mirror was cleared of condensate which was then allowed to re-form (d) the RS232 output of the test hygrometer was monitored until the instrument was seen to have stabilised.

At the conclusion of the final step of the above procedure a set of ten readings was then taken over a period of at least 20 minutes.”

The NPL calibration data is used to generate a calibration curve which is applied to the MBW 973-L output.

4.2.2 Calibration of Buck CR2

The calibration by comparison of the Buck CR2 units is done in a similar way to the NPL calibration described above. In this case, the DG2 is used to generate a flow of air of a fixed dewpoint, which is split between the MBW 973-L and the instrument under test. The flow rate through each instrument is between 0.5 and 1 litres per minute, as measured by the MBW 973-L itself and by a rotameter on the exhaust of the Buck CR2. As for the NPL calibration, the test hygrometer mirror is cleaned beforehand. For each calibration point, which are no more than 20 °C intervals between -50 and +20 °C, the instruments are allowed to stabilise before readings of mirror temperature are recorded over no less than 10 minutes for mirror temperatures below -25 °C, and no less than 5 minutes at temperatures above -25 °C. These readings are logged over RS232 for each instrument, and a mean and standard deviation calculated for each calibration point.

Should the above calibration show a lack of agreement within uncertainty between the MBW 973-L and the Buck CR2, a calibration curve is generated and applied to the Buck CR2 output in processing. Prior to 2021, when one of the Buck CR2 units have not agreed within uncertainty with a calibrated instrument (either at NPL or FAAM), this has been due to a fault with the Buck CR2 (in particular a leak which allows lab air into the chamber, increasing the frost point below -40 °C) and not a calibratable drift, and so a calibration curve was typically not required. During calibration of the Buck CR2-211-M in August 2021, a calibration curve was found to be required, correcting the reported mirror temperature by up to 0.5 °C.

4.3 Data processing

(See `p_rio_buck.py` [FAAM, n.d.] and `p_buck.py` [FAAM, n.d.]

4.3.1 Converting Buck CR2 mirror temperature to volume mixing ratio

The core processed data for the Buck CR2 includes the mirror temperature and the volume mixing ratio of water vapour. Prior to September 2016, the water vapour pressure was calculated using the parameterisation given by Hardy (1998) [Hardy, 1998], which is based on the ITS-90 formulations. In September 2016, v004 of the core data processing was updated to use the Murphy and Koop (2000) [D. M. Murphy, 2005] parameterisation for water vapour pressure. The saturation vapour pressure over liquid water is now calculated according to

$$\ln(e_{s,liq}) = 54.842763 - \frac{6763.22}{T_{mirr}} - 4.210 \ln T_{mirr} + 0.000367 T_{mirr} + \tanh\left(0.0415(T_{mirr} - 218.8)\right)\left(53.878 - \frac{1331.22}{T_{mirr}} - 9.44523 \ln T_{mirr} + 0.014025 T_{mirr}\right) \quad (4.1)$$

valid for $123 < T < 332$ K. The saturation vapour pressure over ice is calculated as follows:

$$\ln(e_{s,ice}) = 9.550426 - \frac{5723.265}{T_{mirr}} + 3.53068 \ln T_{mirr} - 0.00728332 T_{mirr} \quad (4.2)$$

valid above 110 K. The water vapour pressure inside the instrument, $e_{H_2O,Buck}$, is calculated using either equation eq:pliq or eq:pive depending on whether a dew point or a frost point has been observed. Above 273.15 K, a dew point is clearly observed. Below 243.15 K, we can be confident that a frost point is being measured. Between 243.15 and 273.15 K, a dew point is assumed if the mirror has not been below 243.15 K since it was last above 273.15 K and it has been below 273.15 K for less than ten minutes. If the mirror temperature is within the supercooled water regime but has been below 243.15 K since it was last at 273.15 K, or it has been below 273.15 K for more than ten minutes, a frost point is assumed. The fact that these are assumptions is reflected in the measurement uncertainty, described in section ref{uncertainty}.

The vapour pressure is converted to volume mixing ratio, w_{H_2O} , in units of ppm, as follows:

$$w_{H_2O} = 1 \cdot 10^6 \cdot \frac{f e_{H_2O,Buck}}{p_{Buck} - f e_{H_2O,Buck}} \quad (4.3)$$

where f is the relevant enhancement factor¹ given by Hardy (1998) [Hardy, 1998] for either liquid water or ice, p_{Buck} is the air pressure inside the instrument, and $e_{H_2O,Buck}$ is the vapour pressure calculated from the reported

¹ This is the ratio of the pressure of pure water vapour at saturation to the water vapour pressure of saturated moist air.

mirror temperature calculated using equation (4.1) or (4.2). This volume mixing ratio is reported as parameter VMR_CR2 in the core file.

4.3.2 Pressure correction to Buck CR2 dew and frost points

A corrected dew point or frost point of the air outside the aircraft is included in the core data file (parameter TDEWCR2C), which is slightly different to the mirror temperature (approximately 0.2 to 0.6 K higher). This is due to the pressure inside the hygrometer being slightly lower than the outside air pressure since air is drawn through the instrument by a downstream pump. Unlike the General Eastern, the Buck CR2 measures its internal pressure, allowing for a correction to be applied. This correction takes the volume mixing ratio calculated in equation (4.3) and converts it to a water vapour pressure for air outside the aircraft:

$$e_{H_2O, outside} = \frac{p r_{H_2O}}{f + f r_{H_2O}}$$

where p is the static air pressure from the RVSM system in Pa, and r_{H_2O} is the volume mixing ratio from equation (4.3) expressed as a ratio (rather than ppm). A dew or frost point is then calculated using the Murphy and Koop (2005) parameterisation. Frost points are calculated using an equation given in the paper:

$$T_{frost, outside} = \frac{1.814625 \ln e_{H_2O, outside} + 6190.134}{29.120 - \ln e_{H_2O, outside}}$$

In the absence of an equation to calculate dew point, a numerical solving routine is used to find $T_{dew, outside}$ from equation (4.1).

4.4 Uncertainty in Buck CR2 data

The uncertainty associated with the Buck CR2 measurements have several sources, which are summed in quadrature:

- The uncertainty associated with the lab calibration, either performed at NPL or at FAAM using the MBW 973-L transfer standard, calibrated at NPL. This is derived from the NPL expanded uncertainty and fit to a power law: $u(c) = 0.02 + 5 \cdot 10^{27} T_{mirr}^{-12.5}$
- The repeatability of the calibration. This is derived from the NPL calibration measurements of different dew points and fit to a power law: $u(r) = 0.01 + 4 \cdot 10^{19} T_{mirr}^{-9}$
- The response time of the instrument and the atmospheric variability. This is based on an assessment of the standard deviation of subsequent readings over a relevant timescale to give an indication of atmospheric variability. Above 248 K, that relevant timescale is taken to be 8 s. Below 248 K, the timescale is calculated according to $\text{lag} = 2 \cdot 10^{29} T_{mirr}^{-11.902}$. The standard deviation in mirror temperature for the relevant timescale before and after each datapoint is found, and the maximum of these two standard deviations is used as the uncertainty associated with the response time, $u(t)$.
- The uncertainty involved in the interpolation of data between calibration datapoints. This is a function of temperature: above 233.15 K, it is 0.025 K; below 233.15 K it is calculated according to $u(i) = -0.0044 T_{mirr} + 1.051$
- The possible bias, $u(b)$, associated with the uncertainty about whether there is water or ice on the mirror between 243.15 and 273.15 K. This is calculated using a flagging scheme according to the temperature history of the mirror. If the flagging scheme highlights that there is doubt around whether supercooled water or ice has formed on the mirror, the mirror temperature is used to calculate the saturation vapour pressure over water (using the Magnus formula for water), and this saturation vapour pressure is then used to calculate the frost point (using the Magnus formula for ice). The difference between this frost point and the mirror temperature is $u(b)$

These are combined to produce an uncertainty value for the mirror temperature for each datapoint, parameter TDEW_C_U, which is used to calculate an upper and lower bound for the volume mixing ratio, producing an uncertainty parameter VMR_C_U. In v004 of the post processing, this uncertainty was reported as an expanded uncertainty with coverage factor $k = 2$. In v005, for consistency with other uncertainty parameters, it is reported as a combined

uncertainty, which can be doubled by the user for a coverage factor $k = 2$ and coverage probability of approximately 95%.

4.5 Calibration of WVSS-II and associated uncertainty

(See p_wvss2_cal [FAAM, n.d.]

Although the Buck CR2 has the advantage of being an absolute measure of water vapour traceable to national standards, it is slower to respond to atmospheric changes than the WVSS-II. As well as this, the Buck CR2's mode of operation means that fluctuations in the mirror temperature are not an accurate representation of how the water vapour in the atmosphere is changing in the short term. As with all chilled mirror hygrometers, it continually increases and decreases its mirror temperature to determine the point at which a layer of condensate forms. For large changes in dewpoint in particular, this can cause an overshoot and subsequent oscillations which do not reflect real changes in water vapour concentration. The WVSS-II, on the other hand, uses an absorption spectroscopy technique, measuring the absorption due to water vapour in the path of its laser beam. This means that changes in the concentration that the WVSS-II reports are directly caused by atmospheric variation, and so its time response provides a more accurate representation of the true water vapour variation than the Buck CR2.

Unfortunately, it is not straightforward to calibrate the WVSS-II, especially in the lab. The instrument reports volume mixing ratio, but its measurement (i.e. the absorption of the laser beam due to water vapour) is dependent on water vapour pressure. To produce its water vapour mixing ratio data, some unknown internal calculations are performed using the instrument's air pressure measurement. To thoroughly calibrate the WVSS-II, therefore, it would be necessary to make measurements across the water vapour pressure *and* air pressure range of interest. In the FAAM labs, it is not possible to generate a flow of fixed dewpoint air at the pressures encountered in flight (nor is NPL, at present, able to calibrate our MBW 973-L transfer standard at reduced pressure). In the absence of a more satisfactory alternative, we use the Buck CR2 as a calibration source for the WVSS-II by comparison in flight.

This calibration by comparison with the Buck CR2 has been done using data from 21 flights in 2020 when the SN 4252 unit was fitted at window 6 and the Buck CR2 219-M was fitted and working well. The strategy, implemented in wvss2_calibration_v01.py [Price, n.d.] was as follows:

- From the 21 flights' worth of 1 Hz core data, remove (i) any measurements collected in profiles, (ii) any measurements where the RH is greater than 95%, and (iii) 10 minutes of measurements after the RH is above 95%. This is to avoid the effect of the Buck CR2 being slower than the WVSS-II (and thus the instruments reporting water vapour measurements for different altitudes during profiles), and to avoid issues caused by water ingress into either instrument. If either instrument reports three volume mixing ratios below 0 ppm, the following 20 minutes of data are removed from the comparison
- The above step results in a dataset consisting of many chunks of data, separated by no data. It is now possible to assess whether each chunk is of sufficient duration to be an acceptable calibration point. What constitutes a sufficient duration is based on the stabilisation time of the Buck CR2 for the relevant mirror temperature seen in the lab during calibration. If a chunk is long enough, the average of the last 10 s is tested to see whether it could be considered a calibration point. If the standard deviation in the volume mixing ratio over those final 10 s is greater than 2% of the measured volume mixing ratio, the chunk is discarded. Otherwise, its mean is used as a calibration point
- This results in a calibration dataset of WVSS-II vs Buck CR2 volume mixing ratio that can be fit with a cubic polynomial, using a least-squares fitting routine weighted by the uncertainty in the Buck CR2 "calibration point" (which is a combination of the average uncertainty in the Buck CR2 volume mixing ratio for the 10 s, and the standard deviation in the Buck CR2 volume mixing ratio in those 10 s). It was not found to be necessary to include a pressure dependency in the calibration.

Through the above steps a calibrated water vapour volume mixing parameter is created, WVSS2F_VMR_C, that has the time response of the flush-mounted WVSS-II SN 4252 on window 6, along with a link to the traceable calibration of the Buck CR2. This analysis will need to be repeated periodically to monitor for drift. It will also need to be redone for any other WVSS-II unit fitted to the aircraft.

The combined uncertainty associated with the calibration by comparison described above is a combination of three components: (i) the residuals in the cubic fit (calculated using a power law fit to the rolling maximum fractional

residual magnitude), (ii) the minimum uncertainty in the Buck CR2 volume mixing ratio, and (iii) the uncertainty in the fit itself (the likelihood that the true fit to the data provided to the fitting routine lies within this bound). These three sources of uncertainty are summed in quadrature to produce the combined uncertainty in the calibrated flush-mounted WVSS-II, parameter WVSS2F_VMR_C_CU.

4.6 Relative humidity

(See `p_wvss2_rh` [FAAM, n.d.])

In the absence of a reliable relative humidity sensor on the FAAM aircraft, relative humidity must be calculated using independent temperature and water vapour measurements. At present (2021), the fastest core water vapour measurement is that of the flush-mounted WVSS-II, which is calibrated against the Buck CR2 chilled mirror hygrometer as described in section *Calibration of WVSS-II and associated uncertainty*. In the calculation of relative humidity, it is crucial to match water vapour measurements with temperature measurements corresponding to the same parcel of air. The data output from the WVSS-II is updated at a rate of approximately every 2.3 seconds: the internal measurement is made at 4 Hz, but the instrument collects 8 cycles of data (2 s) before doing computations and updating the output. The true air temperature measurements made in the Rosemount Type 102 housings are much faster and are reported at 32 Hz. To match a WVSS-II datapoint with a colocated temperature measurement therefore needs an appropriate lag applied to the temperature data, as well as some averaging.

To find out how long the lag is between the WVSS-II and temperature probe (i.e. the difference in time between the WVSS-II datapoint and its colocated temperature measurement), an analysis was performed (`wvss2_temperature_lag_analysis.py` [Price, n.d.]) using data from 95 flights in 2019 and 2020 when the unit SN 4252 was fitted to the flush inlet at window 6. In these flights there was a mixture of plate- and loom-type PRTs tested (a separate lag analysis being required for looms and plates because of their differing time responses). The raw WVSS-II data (prior to the usual interpolation to 1 Hz) was used in the analysis. Because each reported datapoint in the raw WVSS-II data is an average of 8 cycles (2 seconds), each temperature value to use should be the average of the 64 datapoints leading up to the colocated temperature measurement. This will not necessarily be the temperature measurement with the nearest timestamp, since the WVSS-II takes time to process and transmit data, meaning that the colocated temperature may be logged earlier than the WVSS-II measurement.

As the aircraft moves through the air, there will be sometimes be correlation between the absolute gradients in volume mixing ratio and temperature, and this can be used to determine the lag. For this lag analysis, each of the 95 flights were split into segments 50 WVSS-II datapoints long (approximately 2 minutes). For each segment, a set of 50 corresponding average temperatures is generated by finding the nearest temperature measurement in time to each WVSS-II datapoint, then averaging over the 64 temperature measurements prior. This process is repeated to generate another set of 50 average temperatures, but this time with a lag applied so that the 64 temperature measurements used for each datapoint are $\frac{1}{32}$ s earlier. This is further repeated 320 times, with an incrementally ($\frac{1}{32}$ s) increasing lag for each, until 320 average temperature datasets have been created of different lags (i.e. shifting by $\frac{1}{32}$ s over 10 s). For the WVSS-II dataset for the segment, and the 320 test average temperature datasets for each segment, the absolute gradients in volume mixing ratio and true air temperature, respectively, are calculated.

For each test dataset, the correlation coefficient between volume mixing ratio gradient and true air temperature gradient are calculated. The maximum correlation coefficient for the segment should correspond to the best estimate of the lag. Good estimates of lag are considered to be where this maximum correlation coefficient is greater than 0.7. Where this requirement is satisfied, the lag is recorded, otherwise the segment is discarded. Once all segments in all flights have been analysed, the mean of all of the calculated lags for each type of temperature sensor are found, as well as the standard deviation in those means. The lag to apply to loom true air temperature data was found to be 2.00 ± 0.88 s; the lag to apply to plate true air temperature data was found to be 1.63 ± 1.57 s.

In calculating the relative humidity, `v005` of the post processing code preferentially uses the true air temperature from the de-iced Rosemount Type 102 housing, `TAT_DI_R`. The uncertainty associated with `TAT_DI_R` is described in section *Combined uncertainty in static air temperature*, but in the calculation of relative humidity there is another contributing factor: the uncertainty that comes from trying to match together colocated temperature and water vapour measurements. The lag analysis described above gives an estimate of the lag, with a standard deviation, and so we use this to calculate upper and lower limits of the lag, and subsequently the upper and lower limits of the 2 s smoothed temperature. The uncertainty in temperature due to the uncertainty in lag is then taken to be the greater (in magnitude) of the difference between the upper limit of temperature and the temperature found using the best estimate of the lag, and the difference between the lower limit of temperature and the temperature found

using the best estimate of the lag. In other words, the lag-associated uncertainty in the temperature to use at each datapoint is taken to be the greater of the absolute difference between the temperature to use and the temperature that is the average of the 2 s prior to the upper and lower estimates of lag.

The uncertainty in the temperature that will contribute to the uncertainty in relative humidity is the summation in quadrature of the uncertainty in the true air temperature calculated as described in section *Combined uncertainty in static air temperature*, $u(T_{core})$, and the uncertainty in temperature which comes from uncertainty in the lag applied, $u(T_{lag})$:

$$u(T_{RH}) = \sqrt{u(T_{lag})^2 + u(T_{core})^2}$$

The water vapour pressure, e' , in Pa, is calculated from the calibrated WVSS-II volume mixing ratio (parameter WVSS2F_VMR_C), w , in ppm, and the static pressure from the RVSM system converted to Pa (parameter PS_RVSM $\times 100$), p :

$$e' = \frac{wp \cdot 10^{-6}}{1 + w \cdot 10^{-6}}$$

The uncertainties in the water vapour pressure, $u(e')$, calculated in this way have two sources: $u(w)$, the uncertainty in the calibrated WVSS-II volume mixing ratio in ppm (parameter WVSS2F_VMR_C_CU), and $u(p)$, the uncertainty in the RVSM static pressure in Pa (given by equation (2.5), multiplied by 100 to convert from mb to Pa).

$$u(e') = \sqrt{\left(\frac{p}{(1 + w \cdot 10^{-6})^2}\right)^2 \cdot (u(w) \cdot 10^{-6})^2 + \left(\frac{w \cdot 10^{-6}}{1 + w \cdot 10^{-6}}\right)^2 \cdot (u(p))^2}$$

The pure saturation vapour pressure, $e_{s,liq}$ and $e_{s,ice}$, is again calculated according to Murphy and Koop (2005), using equations (4.1) and (4.2).

The temperature to use here is the 2 s averaged, lag-applied temperature calculated to be colocated with each WVSS-II datapoint. Uncertainties in these saturation vapour pressures are calculated as follows:

$$u(e_{s,liq}) = \frac{\partial e_{s,liq}}{\partial T} \cdot u(T_{RH})$$

$$u(e_{s,ice}) = \frac{\partial e_{s,ice}}{\partial T} \cdot u(T_{RH})$$

For brevity, the partial derivatives are not written out here but can be found in the v005 post processing code.

Now we multiply the pure saturation vapour pressures calculated above by the enhancement factors for each phase, to give the effective saturation vapour pressures, e'_s :

$$e'_{s,liq,T>273} = f_{s,liq,T>273} e_{s,liq}$$

$$e'_{s,liq,T<273} = f_{s,liq,T<273} e_{s,liq}$$

$$e'_{s,ice} = f_{s,ice} e_{s,ice}$$

where $e'_{s,liq,T>273}$ is the effective saturation vapour pressure over liquid water above 273 K, $e'_{s,liq,T<273}$ is the effective saturation vapour pressure over supercooled water, and $e'_{s,ice}$ is the effective saturation vapour pressure over ice. The corresponding enhancement factor for each phase, f is calculated as described by Hardy [Hardy, 1998] for each phase of water, ranging from 1.001 to 1.005 for the conditions in which FAAM flies.

Hyland [Hyland, 1975] estimates the percentage maximum uncertainty in calculated enhancement factor at 1 bar (no data is provided at lower pressures) as 0.01, 0.03, 0.04, 0.05, 0.06% at 30, 10, -10, -30 and -50 °C, respectively. There will also be uncertainty in f due to the uncertainty in p , T and e_s , as follows:

$$u(f_{T,e,p}) = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial T}\right)^2 u(T)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial e_s}\right)^2 u(e_s)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial p}\right)^2 (u(p))^2}$$

When these are all calculated, and summed in quadrature with the uncertainty estimated by Hyland [Hyland, 1975], this gives uncertainties in f between 0.00025 and 0.00065. This is negligible in comparison with the contribution

to the uncertainty in RH from the uncertainty in the vapour pressure and the uncertainty from temperature, so instead of lengthy calculations in the post processing code we use the upper limit of 0.00065.

The relative humidity over each phase of water is calculated as follows:

$$RH_{liq,T>273} = 100 \frac{e'}{e'_{s,liq,T>273}} = 100 \frac{e'}{f_{s,liq,T>273} e_{s,liq}}$$

$$RH_{liq,T<273} = 100 \frac{e'}{e'_{s,liq,T<273}} = 100 \frac{e'}{f_{s,liq,T<273} e_{s,liq}}$$

$$RH_{ice} = 100 \frac{e'}{e'_{s,ice}} = 100 \frac{e'}{f_{s,ice} e_{s,ice}}$$

These are parameters RH_LIQ and RH_ICE in the core file.

The uncertainty in the two relative humidities, parameters RH_LIQ_CU and RH_ICE_CU, are calculated using:

$$u(RH) = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial RH}{\partial e'}\right)^2 u(e')^2 + \left(\frac{\partial RH}{\partial f}\right)^2 u(f)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial RH}{\partial e_s}\right)^2 u(e_s)^2}$$

which becomes:

$$u(RH) = \sqrt{\left(\frac{RH}{e'}\right)^2 u(e')^2 + \left(\frac{RH}{f}\right)^2 u(f)^2 + \left(\frac{RH}{e_s}\right)^2 u(e_s)^2} \quad (4.4)$$

where the RH , e' , f and e_s are calculated as appropriate for the relevant phase of water.

Fig. 4.1 and Fig. 4.3 show the relative contributions of each term in equation (4.4) for two different flights, with data from these two flights shown in Fig. 4.2 and Fig. 4.4. It can be seen that the terms associated with uncertainty in vapour pressure and saturation vapour pressure are the largest, while the contribution from the uncertainty associated with the enhancement factor is negligible. Comparing Fig. 4.1 and Fig. 4.2, with Fig. 4.3 and Fig. 4.4, respectively, illustrates the variability in the uncertainty in relative humidity, and the contributing factors. Depending on the conditions encountered, the uncertainty in saturation vapour pressure (which comes from uncertainty in temperature) can be more or less important than the uncertainty in vapour pressure (which comes mostly from the uncertainty in the WVSS-II volume mixing ratio). Uncertainty in relative humidity is generally highest when WVSS-II volume mixing ratio is low, as the relative uncertainty in that measurement increases as volume mixing ratio decreases.

Fig. 4.1: Relative contributions of each term in equation (4.4) over the course of C128.

Fig. 4.2: Temperature and humidity data for C128.

Fig. 4.3: Relative contributions of each term in equation (4.4) over the course of C213.

Fig. 4.4: Temperature and humidity data for C128.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- [1] JCGM 200:2012. International vocabulary of metrology - Basic and general concepts and associated terms (VIM), 3rd edition. 2012.
- [2] V. Dreiling A. Giez, M. Zöger and C. Mallaun. Static Source Error Calibration of a Nose Boom Mounted Air Data System on an Atmospheric Research Aircraft Using the Trailing Cone Method. *Forschungsbericht 2019-07, Deutsches Zentrum für Luft- und Raumfahrt Flugexperimente*, 2019.
- [3] UK Civil Aviation Authority. Application guidance and information about Reduced Vertical Separation Minimum (RVSM). <https://www.caa.co.uk/Commercial-industry/Aircraft/Operations/Navigation-approvals/RVSM/>.
- [4] Jens Bange, Marco Esposito, Donald H. Lenschow, Philip R. A. Brown, Volker Dreiling, Andreas Giez, Larry Mahrt, Szymon P. Malinowski, Alfred R. Rodi, Raymond A. Shaw, Holger Siebert, Herman Smit, and Martin Zöger. *Measurement of Aircraft State and Thermodynamic and Dynamic Variables*, chapter 2, pages 7–75. John Wiley & Sons, Ltd. URL: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/abs/10.1002/9783527653218.ch2>, arXiv:<https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.1002/9783527653218.ch2>, doi:<https://doi.org/10.1002/9783527653218.ch2>.
- [5] S. Bell. The Beginner's Guide to Uncertainty of Measurement, NPL Good Practice Guide No. 11. *National Physical Laboratory*, 2001.
- [6] D. Khelif C. A. Friehe. Fast-response aircraft temperature sensors. *Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology*, 9(6):784–795, 1992.
- [7] C. A. Friehe D. Khelif, S. P. Burns. Improved Wind Measurements on Research Aircraft. *Journal of Atmospheric and Oceanic Technology*, 16:860, 1998.
- [8] T. Koop D. M. Murphy. Review of the vapour pressures of ice and supercooled water for atmospheric applications. *Quarterly Journal of the Royal Meteorological Society*, 131:1539–1565, 2005.
- [9] K. N. Robertson D. N. Ferguson. BAe 146-301 E3001 Atmospheric Research Aircraft Certificate of Airworthiness Report No. 220 RVSM. Technical Report ATEST03428, BAE Systems, 2004.
- [10] FAAM. decades-pp post processing v004. <https://github.com/ncasuk/decades-pp>.
- [11] FAAM. decades-pp rio_buck_cr2 post processing module. https://github.com/ncasuk/decades-pp/blob/master/ppodd/pod/p_rio_buck.py.
- [12] FAAM. decades-pp rio_temps post processing module. https://github.com/ncasuk/decades-pp/blob/master/ppodd/pod/p_rio_temps.py.
- [13] FAAM. decades-ppandas BuckCR2 post processing module. https://github.com/FAAM-146/decades-ppandas/blob/v0.10.2/ppodd/pod/p_buck.py.
- [14] FAAM. decades-ppandas PRTTemperatureUncertainties post processing module. https://github.com/FAAM-146/decades-ppandas/blob/v0.10.2/ppodd/pod/p_prt_uncertainties.py.
- [15] FAAM. decades-ppandas PRTTemperatures post processing module. https://github.com/FAAM-146/decades-ppandas/blob/v0.10.2/ppodd/pod/p_prt_temps.py.

- [16] FAAM. decades-ppandas RecoveryFactor post processing module. https://github.com/FAAM-146/decades-ppandas/blob/v0.10.2/ppodd/pod/p_recovery_factor.py.
- [17] FAAM. decades-ppandas WVSS2Calibrated post processing module. https://github.com/FAAM-146/decades-ppandas/blob/v0.10.2/ppodd/pod/p_wvss2_cal.py.
- [18] FAAM. decades-ppandas WVSS2RH post processing module. https://github.com/FAAM-146/decades-ppandas/blob/v0.10.2/ppodd/pod/p_wvss2_rh.py.
- [19] FAAM. decades-ppandas post processing v005. <https://github.com/FAAM-146/decades-ppandas>. doi:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5711136>.
- [20] D. N. Ferguson. AVRO 146-RJ All Series Certificate of Airworthiness Report No. 210 Reduced Vertical Separation Minimum (RVSM). Technical Report MFT-E-R-460-3696, BAE Systems, 2000.
- [21] D. N. Ferguson. BAe 146-301 E3001 Atmospheric Research Aircraft Certificate of Airworthiness Report Number 217, Static Pressure Errors. Technical Report ATEST03429, BAE Systems, 2004.
- [22] B. Hardy. ITS-90 formulations for vapor pressure, frostpoint temperature, dewpoint temperature, and enhancement factors in the range -100 to +100 C. *The Proceedings of the Third International Symposium on Humidity and Moisture, National Physical Laboratory*, 1998.
- [23] R. W. Hyland. A correlation for the Second Interaction Virial Coefficients and Enhancement Factors for Moist Air. *Journal of Research of National Bureau of Standards - A. Physics and Chemistry*, 1975.
- [24] ISO/IEC. Guide 98-3 Uncertainty of Measurement - Part 3: Guide to the expression of uncertainty in measurements (GUM:1995). 2008.
- [25] M. E. Poole. BAe 146 Series 300 Certificate of Airworthiness Report No. 126. Technical Report HFD-R-463-8211, BAE Systems, 1988.
- [26] H. C. Price. Variable Recovery Factor code, PRT only, v01. https://github.com/FAAM-146/faam-core-met/blob/main/deiced_recovery_factor_prt_only_2021.py.
- [27] H. C. Price. WVSS-II and temperature lag analysis. https://github.com/FAAM-146/faam-core-met/blob/main/wvss2_temperature_lag_analysis.py.
- [28] H. C. Price. WVSS-II in-flight calibration analysis, v01. https://github.com/FAAM-146/faam-core-met/blob/main/wvss2_calibration_v01.py.
- [29] D. I. Thompson T. M. Stickney, M. W. Shedlov. Rosemount Total Temperature Sensors, Technical Report 5755. *Rosemount Aerospace Inc.*, 1994.